

Kinetics of Thermal Decomposition of UO_3 : Part II. $\beta\text{-UO}_3$ *

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Kinetics of thermal decomposition of $\beta\text{-UO}_3$ was studied using thermogravimetry and differential thermal analysis techniques. Unlike the α form¹, $\beta\text{-UO}_3$ decomposed directly to U_3O_8 . The decomposition followed first order kinetics. The specific reaction rate constant K_r could be expressed in terms of the activation energy and the pre-exponential factor by the equation

$$K_r (\text{Sec}^{-1}) = 7.25 \times 10^{19} \exp \frac{-89,300}{RT}$$

In continuation of our studies on the thermal stabilities of various modifications of uranium trioxide¹, the results of the kinetics of thermal decomposition of $\beta\text{-UO}_3$ are reported.

$\beta\text{-UO}_3$ used in the present study was obtained by thermal decomposition of ammonium diuranate at 500° for 3 hr. Ammonium diuranate was precipitated from uranyl nitrate solution, filtered without washing and decomposed. The precipitate washed free of nitrate ions gave amorphous UO_3 ².

The X-ray diffraction pattern obtained (Table I) was found to be in good agreement with that reported for $\beta\text{-UO}_3$ by Debets³ and by Hoekstra and Siegel⁴. The X-ray pattern was recorded on a Philips wide angle X-ray diffractometer using filtered $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation from a fully stabilized Philips PW 1010 X-ray generator.

Using volumetric method⁵, the oxygen-to-uranium ratio was found to be 3.007.

Thermogravimetric curves were obtained with the Stanton thermobalance of 1 mg sensitivity at a constant heating rate of $4^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. Since the transformation of $\beta\text{-UO}_3$ to U_3O_8 involved only 1.83% weight loss, large amount of sample had to be used. In the present case 3 gms of sample was used.

Apparatus for obtaining differential thermal analysis curve has been described earlier⁶. Honeywell Brown X₁, X₂ recorder with a span of 1 mV was used to obtain the D.T.A. curve with the same heating rate. 1 gm of the sample was used for D.T.A.

Results: The curve for thermal decomposition of $\beta\text{-UO}_3$ is shown in fig. 1. For the sake of convenience the curve is shown for temperatures beyond 500° since below that temperature no weight changes are obtained for the dried specimen. It is seen that $\beta\text{-UO}_3$

*Paper presented at the Annual Convention, Indian Chemical Society, held in Anand in November, 1966.

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TABLE I

X-ray powder diffractometer pattern of $\beta-UO_3$

Debets ³	Hoekstra and Siegel ⁴		Observed values	
	d(A°)	I/I _o	d(A°)	I/I _o
7.138	7.225	VW	7.138	17
5.096	5.096	VVW	5.096	6
4.796	4.796	VW	4.783	29
4.332				
4.162			4.152	8
3.867	3.969	VVW		
3.723	3.739	VW	3.708	16
3.576	3.590	S	3.576	67
3.480				
3.433	3.440	W	3.433	20
3.401	3.401	WM	3.401	53
3.089	3.099	VW	3.089	5
3.068	3.074	WM	3.068	85
3.023	3.038	WM	3.032	100
2.998			2.998	< 5
2.931			2.931	< 5
2.867			2.849	5
2.814			2.779	5
2.755			2.746	5
2.726			2.714	5
2.659			2.637	5
2.622				
2.546			2.542	5
2.508	2.508	VW	2.508	< 5
2.495			2.495	24
2.475				
2.465	2.468	VW	2.468	32
2.420			2.417	< 5
2.389			2.383	< 5
2.298				
2.251				
2.248				
2.232				
2.188				
2.161				
2.073				
2.021				
2.002	2.006	VVW	2.006	< 5
1.987				
1.957	1.957	W	1.957	5
1.937	1.945	VW	1.939	42
1.931				
1.912	1.916	VW	1.916	32
1.901			1.903	32
1.890	1.890	VW	1.895	27
1.884			1.884	21
1.868			1.866	15
1.805	1.807	VVW	1.807	6

starts decomposing above 545°, the decomposition is complete at about 625°. This temperature is in good agreement with that reported by Wheeler et al⁷. Differential

Fig. 1.

TG and DTG curves for the thermal decomposition of β - UO_3 .

thermal analysis showed a single endothermic peak commencing at 550° and terminating at 635° (Fig 2).

Fig. 2

DTA curve for the thermal decomposition of β - UO_3 .

The rate dependent parameters i.e. order of reaction (n), activation energy (ΔE) and entropy of activation (ΔS) were obtained from the differential thermal analysis and thermogravimetric curves.

Order of reaction: Since the decomposition reaction is not accompanied by other

reactions which might affect the shape of the D.T.A. peak, the order of reaction was calculated using the Kissinger's shape index method⁸ which gives a reasonably approximate value under such a condition.

According to Kissinger⁸, the order of reaction (n) is given by the relation

$$n = 1.26 \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

a/b is known as the shape index and is obtained as shown in fig. 2. The order of reaction obtained by this method is found to be 0.89 i.e. approximately unity.

The order of reaction from thermogravimetric curve was calculated following the method of Horowitz and Metzger⁹, by determining the fraction unreacted at the temperature T_i at which the rate of weight loss (dW/dT) with respect to temperature is maximum. This fraction was found to be 0.382 which is close to the theoretical value of 0.362 for a first order kinetics.

The apparent order of the decomposition reaction is thus found from both T.G. and D.T.A. to be unity.

Activation Energy: The activation energy for decomposition was obtained by the method of Fuoss et al.¹⁰. According to them, for first order, the activation energy ΔE is given by the relation

$$\Delta E = - \frac{RT_i^2}{W_i} \left(\frac{dW}{dT} \right)_i \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

and the frequency factor Z is expressed in terms of the activation energy by the relation

$$Z = \frac{a}{w_i} \left(\frac{dW}{dT} \right)_i \exp \frac{\Delta E}{RT_i} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where a=heating rate,

T_i=temperature of inflexion i.e. the temperature at which the rate of weight loss dW/dT with respect to temperature is maximum;

W_i=weight loss from the point of inflexion on the thermogravimetric curve upto the end of reaction and (dW/dT)_i=rate of weight loss at the point of inflexion.

Unlike earlier method¹¹ involving determination of slopes at a number of points along the T.G. curve, this method requires the evaluation of slope at a single point, viz. the point of inflexion. Since the curve at this point is almost linear, it is possible to determine the slope with greater accuracy. Moreover, unlike other methods⁹⁻¹², this method does not involve calculation of any special function of α-the fraction reacted as a function of temperature.

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10. R. M. Fuoss, I. O. Salyer and H. S. Wilson, *J. Polymer Science Pt (A)* 1964, **2(7)**, 3147.

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12. A. W. Coats and J. P. Redfern, *Nature*, 1964, **201**, 68.

Substituting the values of T_1 , W , and $(dW/dT)_1$ obtained from fig 1 in equation 2, the activation energy ΔE was found to be 87 (8 K cal/mole. As a check, the activation energy was also computed using the method of Coats and Redfern¹² (fig. 3) which gave a value of 91 47 K cal/mole, in reasonable agreement with the above value. The mean value of 89 3 K cal/mole was therefore used in subsequent calculations.

Fig. 3

Coats and Redfern plot for first order kinetics.

From equation 3, the frequency factor for the decomposition was calculated to be $7.25 \times 10^{19} \text{ sec}^{-1}$.

Using the interrelationship¹³ of the frequency factor Z with the entropy of activation ΔS , the latter was calculated to be $+31.4 \text{ e.u.}$

DISCUSSION

Unlike the α form which decomposes with the intermediate formation of $\text{UO}_{2.9}$, the β - UO_3 decomposes in a single step to U_3O_8 . From the rate dependent parameters obtained above the specific reaction rate K_r could be expressed by the equation

$$K_r (\text{sec}^{-1}) = 7.25 \times 10^{19} \exp \frac{-89,300}{RT}$$

As in the decomposition of $\text{UO}_{2.9}$, the observed frequency factor of 7.25×10^{19} is much higher than the values normally encountered for the reactions in gases and solutions.

Shannon¹⁴ has reviewed the decomposition of a number of solids and tried to explain the high values for some of the decompositions using the 'Activated Complex Theory'. However, his theory cannot explain the values which are much too high as in the present case and as observed in other decompositions like those of calcium oxalate¹⁵ and of a number of bromates¹⁶.

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16. G. M. Bancroft and H. D. Gesser, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 1545.

Because of the dependence of kinetic parameters on a number of factors such as heating rate¹⁷, sample container geometry¹⁸, sample size¹⁹ etc., it is considered that not much significance can be attached to the absolute values of these parameters. Nevertheless these could be used for intercomparison of thermal stabilities of the compounds studied under identical conditions.

The X-ray diffractometer patterns of $\alpha\text{-UO}_3$ and $\text{UO}_{2.9}$ are very much similar¹. The two substances therefore may be assumed to have nearly identical crystal structures. The structure of $\alpha\text{-UO}_3$ is reported to be hexagonal²⁰ whereas $\beta\text{-UO}_3$ is indexed on the basis of mono-clinic cell³ with the space group of either $P2_1 (C_2^2)$ or $P2_1/m (C_2^2h)$. Hence compared to $\beta\text{-UO}_3$, $\text{UO}_{2.9}$ by its similarity with $\alpha\text{-UO}_3$ can be assumed to have higher symmetry. Hence the activation energy needed to bring about the decomposition of $\text{UO}_{2.9}$ can be expected to be higher than that for $\beta\text{-UO}_3$. The observed values are 108 Kcal/mole in case of $\text{UO}_{2.9}$ and 89.3 Kcal/mole in case of $\beta\text{-UO}_3$. Comparison of the kinetic parameters of $\beta\text{-UO}_3$ with those of α form has not been made since the latter decomposes with the formation of intermediate $\text{UO}_{2.9}$.

The authors thank Dr. J. Shankar, Head, Chemistry Division for his interest in this work.

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Received, August 19, 1967

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